

How Breathing Rate Associate With Beauty Loving Behavior?

Warisha Amjad* & Muhammad Imran Qadir

Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan
Corresponding Author (Warisha Amjad) - warisharana786@gmail.com*

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.46431/MEJAST.2022.5407>

Copyright © 2022 Warisha Amjad & Muhammad Imran Qadir. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Article Received: 22 November 2022

Article Accepted: 19 December 2022

Article Published: 24 December 2022

ABSTRACT

Basic aim of the current study was to link the breathing rate with beauty. 100 subjects were took part in this project. All candidates belong to the educational department of biology. People with breathing rate 25 should be interested in beauty loving behavior. While very few of them was not interested in good looks.

Keywords: Breathing; Research; Beauty.

INTRODUCTION

Respiratory rate is the number of breathing that we take in a minute. The normal respiratory rate for an adult person is 12 to 20 breathings in a minute. It has been studied that during crying, sleeping has great influence on the breathing rate. The problem of lungs leads to heavy breathing.

The topic of beauty is very common now days. Many people like beauty and few of them does not interested in outer shell. These people like the inner beauty of human soul.

The nature of beauty is most important in Western philosophy. And they measure the beauty with honesty, justice and goodness.

The objective of the present study was to correlate the beauty with breathing rate of human being.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Total 100 subjects were taking part in this study.

In this process we check our breathing rate. We count our breathings by using stop watch and we count our respiratory rate per minute.

STUDY DESIGN

A total of 100 students were take part in this process. A questionnaire was prepared which contain questions related to good looks and breathing rate.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

It is performed by using M state. The results are compiled and given as under.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

100 subjects were participated in this project. *test* should be performed and the *P value* shows that the result was not significant. And different result was given in Graph 1 and Graph 2.

Graph 1 - This graph symbolizes the girl’s likeness or unlikeness toward beauty

Graph 2 - This graph represents the boy’s likeness or unlikeness toward beauty

CONCLUSION

The present study shows that people with breathing rate 25 was interested in beauty while very few of them do not like it.

Declarations

Source of Funding

This research work did not receive any grant from funding agencies in the public or not-for-profit sectors.

Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare no competing financial, professional, or personal interests.

Consent for publication

The authors declare that they consented to the publication of this research work.

Authors’ Contributions

All authors equally contributed to research and paper drafting.

References

- [1] Qadir MI, Malik SA (2010). Comparison of alterations in red blood cell count and alterations in hemoglobin concentration in patients suffering from rectal carcinoma undergoing 5-fluorouracil and folic acid therapy. *Pharmacology online*, N1 3: 240-243.
- [2] Qadir MI, Noor A (2018). *Anemia's. Rare & Uncommon Diseases*. Cambridge Scholars Publishing. Newcastle, England. ISBN: 978-1-5275-1807-0.
- [3] Qadir MI, Javid A (2018). Awareness about Crohn's Disease in biotechnology students. *GloAdv Res J Med Medical Sci*, 7(3): 062-064.
- [4] Qadir MI, Saleem A (2018). Awareness about ischemic heart disease in university biotechnology students. *GloAdv Res J Med Medical Sci*, 7(3): 059-061.
- [5] Qadir MI, Ishfaq S (2018). Awareness about hypertension in biology students. *Int J Mod Pharma Res*, 7(2): 08-10.
- [6] Qadir MI, Mehwish (2018). Awareness about psoriasis disease. *Int J Mod Pharma Res*, 7(2): 17-18.
- [7] Qadir MI, Shahzad R (2018). Awareness about obesity in postgraduate students of biotechnology. *Int J Mod Pharma Res*, 7(2): 14-16.
- [8] Qadir MI, Rizvi M (2018). Awareness about thalassemia in post graduate students. *MOJ Lymphology & Phlebology*, 2(1): 14-16.
- [9] Qadir MI, Ghalia BA (2018). Awareness survey about colorectal cancer in students of M. Phil Biotechnology at Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan. *Nov Appro in Can Study*, 1(3): NACS.000514.2018.
- [10] Qadir MI, Saba G (2018). Awareness about intestinal cancer in university student. *Nov Appro in Can Study*.